

CAREER TRANSITION PROGRAM OF STUDENTS WITH HEARING IMPAIRMENT

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Abstract: Career transition is one program that can highlight the skills and abilities of students with special needs in the field of employment. Talent and abilities available to them should always be polished and supervised to ensure that they get the same opportunities as those that are normal. This research is using qualitative survey design. Career transition program is a program that helps students with special needs to get a job after school. Data collected through the observation of the study participants as well as face to face interviews with employers, employees, parents and teachers at school.

Participants of the study is a student with hearing impairment who is working in a kindergarten. A skills training module was developed as a guide to the study participants carrying out the work at one of the selected nurseries. The study found that the participant can master all the skills as required by the employer. Face to face interview findings also indicate a positive outlook on career transition program that has been carried out. The study also suggests a number of improvements to enhance the effectiveness of career transition program in the future.

Keywords: *career transition program, students with hearing problems.*

INTRODUCTION

Career transition is a program that can highlight the skills and abilities of students with special needs in the field of employment. Talent and abilities of special needs should always be polished and supervised to ensure that they get the same opportunities as those that are normal. Careful preparation will help students with special needs to get jobs that match their skills and abilities. In Malaysia, the government's commitment to help the disabled into workforce implemented through Technical and Vocational Education Program from the school level up to the vocational training institutions. The goal of a career transition program is intended to complement the skills to live independently for special education students. It is part of the effort to complete a special education students with skills that can help them to improve their self-worth in the job market when they graduate from school. Walls and Fullimer (1997) stated that a variety of skills can be applied to these groups to provide opportunities for them to work and live independently. Students with special needs have the right to be given the opportunity to prove that they are able to live independently like others. According Safani and Salleh (2000), disability experienced by students with special needs is a major obstacle to their work. However, they need to be assisted by a team of transition so that they gain the

confidence to continue working while getting some experience and exposure.

The model used in this study is a model taken from the educational psychology. According Muhibbin Shah (2010), before embarking on skills training and transition of students, application and use levels of teaching in teaching skills is very important. The stages in the process of teaching is closely associated with the use of teaching strategies. The point is that any use of teaching strategies must be between a strong network in the level of teaching. This model emphasizes the teaching of the three stages: the first is phase of preparation, the second phase is implementation and the third phase is an evaluation. The Module help researchers conducting this study regularly and systematically. Pre teaching is preparation before implementation of the activities. The final stage is the stage of evaluation and further action. This stage is the assessment of learning outcomes after teaching and follow-up action. Construction of a career transition module is also built on the module of the stages of this teaching.

PROBLEMS STATEMENT AND RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

Various factors have been identified as the cause of the hearing impaired group does not get the job. Attitudinal factors are believed to play an important role in efforts

to find work for these people. Humility and not sure of what had caused these people difficult to succeed in any field of endeavour. According to Noraini, Khalid and Nor Aishah (2001), education and training opportunities to people with special needs are very limited. Existing education programs meet the needs of the market and its economic development. This is due to the lack of cognitive ability level of the hearing impaired group and unable to absorb and getting jobs.

The economic and social changes taking place also have an impact on them. This assertion is supported by a study conducted by Safani and Salleh (2000) which states that the attitude of people with special needs is also the cause of the problems unemployment problems to them. They are more likely to be with friends in the same boat if you want to venture into a field. This shows that they lack of confidence in their abilities and their own ability to work with a group of other normal. Therefore, they will be focused on a particular type of work without thinking of the other requirements that can guarantee the future when venturing into the working world. Yaeda (2010) suggested a number of strategies that might work for a better career transitions among them are giving students the opportunity to try something new. In addition, teaching skills in technical and vocational education is also greatly affect the interests and aptitudes in this transition program.

The objective of this study is to train students with disabilities with a variety of skills that can put them in the employment sector as well as to learn the skills as quickly as possible and be able to apply them in the workplace. In addition, this study can foster self-reliance and more confident with him/herself and those around them. The specific objectives of this case study is to review the capacity and capabilities for the hearing impaired pupils adapt the workforce after graduating from school.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in the form of qualitative methods using survey design. Data collected through the observation of the study participants as well as face to face interviews with employers, employees, parents and teachers at school. According Alias (2008), the observation method has high reliability if collected in a systematic and orderly manner in the actual study situation. Previous observations, researchers have conducted a study of the implementation of the course such as search and selection of employers, student selection, skills training and experience in transition program. The researcher has received approval from the parents and choosing the appropriate employers to ensure that research can be carried out smoothly and orderly. The Employers chosen was a businessman nurseries or child care centre. After the approval of the employer, the discussion on the scope of work and related jobs skills were discussed. In addition, the selection of participants was based on intelligence, abilities,

talents, attitudes, behaviors, interests and abilities of students in performing a variety of skills. According to Reber (1998), defined as the quotient of students psychophysical ability to respond to stimuli or adapt to the environment in an appropriate manner. The level of intelligence would determine the level of students' ability to learn whether the child belongs to the gifted or talented child. Students selected as in this study was a female student who was 14 years old with hearing problem since birth. Ability to adapt to the social community, characteristics of a good listen and follow instructions, able to work independently and has a distinctive flair to the researcher to select the option to undergo this study.

The study was conducted over four weeks, involving 20 working days in which study participants will be sent to work and assisting in the nursery. In addition, the researchers also conducted several pre training program based on the module designed to test the participant abilities. The modules are built are based on training given to students during working in nurseries. The researchers will make observations of the study participants based on the module. Among the modules that are built are:

- i. Skills in cleaning and sweeping
- ii. Skills in training mopping the floor
- iii. Skills washing dishes
- iv. Skills training in making a bed
- v. Folding and stacking skills training
- vi. Updating skills training room
- vii. Skills training in making cup of milk
- viii. Skills training child care

Evaluation is done by observation in terms of ability to work, enthusiasm and communication when students are working in nurseries. The purpose of the assessment is to see the students' ability to adapt in the employment sector and in rural communities. Researchers have made several times by observations skills training given and the work that is done in nurseries. This is to ensure that skills training and work carried out can have a positive impact on students.

In addition, the researchers also conducted face to face interviews with employers, workers nurseries, parents of students in kindergarten and school teachers study participants to obtain firsthand information. Interviews are a method of study is important because it helps researchers explore and get in-depth study. According to Fontana and Frey (1994), there are three types of interviews namely structured interviews, semi-structured interviews and unstructured interviews.

RESEARCH FINDINGS

Observations

Through observations made during the four weeks, the researchers found that modules built specifically for the study participants can be used properly. Each

training skills can be fully controlled. Researchers continue to monitor and guide the students, the career transition training is conducted. Before going to work, students have undergone training in the hostel twice.

The first skills training involves cleaning work such as sweeping, mopping the floor, washing the dishes and tidy up or dorm room at the hostel. From the first observation, study participants were able to hold the broom and mop handle properly, mopping floors and washing dishes to clean.

Session work in nurseries that are conducted by participant ranged from 2.00 to 6.00 pm on working days. During the session, the researchers observe and record all skills that can be mastered by the study participants during their career transition training in the nursery. From the observation during the day to work, study participants can adapt to other workers and children in nurseries.

Participants began to work on the first day to do the cleaning work such as folding blankets and clothes for children and put them in the closet. In the next days, the study participants were asked to bathe and make milk to children in the nursery. Each training skills they have learned in the dorms can be practiced by study participants with both while at work. Many children in nurseries showed a positive attitude to the study participants. This is because the study participants was a warm friendly and accessible to anyone.

INTERVIEWS

Face to face interviews for the study was conducted on four interviews with survey participants, namely the employer, an interview with one of the parents of students in kindergarten, nursery workers, interviews with teachers and interviews with study participants. This interview is to get in-depth information. Here is the interview received by the researcher:

The interview was conducted interviews Employers: "This program is very good and gives a lot of advantages from various quarters. I get a new experience because this is the first time I meet students who have hearing problems. Indirectly, I can learn and develop knowledge in sign language and recognize the special education students more closely. Participant is still capable of doing what he was told and very hard to treat children in the nurseries of mine. I suggest, after this if there is any employer who wants to hire people working, we can receive a special child like this because they are just like other normal people. From my part, too, I'll get them to help them make a living for themselves as well as to get to know the outside world (in addition to their world). A good program and should be continued in order to protect the welfare of disabled people from time to time".

Parents of students in kindergarten: "I was an administrative clerk in the primary. On the day I took my son, I was quite surprised to see his son was led by a new employee to get to the car. This is because before my son was not friendly with anyone except

with workers in nurseries only. I feel excited about the ability of these students being able to treat my son and get closer to him. To me, this program should always be given the supervision and guidance to ensure that workers in these groups can work well. "

Nursery Worker: "career transition program is an incredible experience for us as a nursery worker. We never had to deal with students like this especially special education students. It's a bit much to open the eyes of the community and realize that these special kids just like other children. We really like to be able to learn a few words in sign language with this student. Although we find it difficult to communicate with these students, the assistance provided by the researchers as signal card with a photo can help us understand a little bit of sign language deaf people. In our view, this transition student is a child-friendly and easy to treat the brothers in nurseries well. At first the students were very difficult to adapt with them, but after a few days the students can mingle with them well. "

School Teacher: "I was the class teacher. In my opinion, a career transition program like this can give the real experience to students. At least the students can be ready when they are in the outside world, especially after school later. Students are able to distinguish between right and wrong as well as to become more confident and willing to confront the outside world. Special education teachers are also proposed in order to carry out this kind of career transition program to other students to help students with special needs succeed as mainstream students. I also, the federal, state and PPD can develop this program more widely in the future. "

Through the above interview, study participants gave positive comments on the career transition program carried out by the researcher. Special skills training to career is very important to give a chance to these people. According to Jesus, Z. M., Salleh, N., Mustapha, R., & Yassin, H. M. (2009), career fields in the future is focused on the expertise available in the individual itself. It is to help every individual that outline the talents and abilities of each while finding a good job in supporting our daily lives. According to Hiller (2007); Melissa, Shier, Graham & Jones (2009) and Zainuddin Mohd Isa (2009), among these skills are skills in communication and problem solving skills in behavior, teamwork, time management, self-confidence, can follow instructions and confronts the community social. In addition, people with special needs can also be decided to determine their own life as a worker and member of the local community.

DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, it can be concluded that the career transition program is a training program that is crucial in helping people with special needs, especially students from the school. Each skill training provided specifically to help them learn a real job

situation. Based on the findings, some suggestions that can be done to improve this program is:

- i. The ministry, states and districts should work together and play an important role in the development of this career transition program and to maintain the stability of technical and vocational education programs that have been implemented.
- ii. Construction modules that match their abilities and interests of students with disabilities are strongly encouraged to help them carry out skills training in line with the abilities and capabilities available to them.
- iii. Employment agencies of the public sector and the private sector is expected to provide opportunities for students with special needs is a taste of life in the working world on par with a normal human to another by holding workshops or specialized training on a career with the cooperation developed with other agencies non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and associations -persatuan others.
- iv. Support education and employment support for career transition program can be implemented in Malaysia to meet the needs of students with special needs. It is a key element in ensuring the success of the transition from school to the working world through a combination or a combination of educational support and employment support.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the study of the career transition program is a major impact for people with special needs in particular hearing impaired students who have difficulty in communicating with outsiders. A lot of experience can serve as a guide when they venture into the job in the future. Involvement and responsibility of all parties is crucial in ensuring a career transition program is progressing well from time to time as well as to meet the needs of the disabled. Circular or related module transition program shall be prepared for a more structured implementation.

This program should be promoted to help students with special needs learn to live independently in line with normal students. Exposure to this program should also be extended to all parties, especially the teachers, the parents, departments and job-related agenda. The exposure can be demonstrated is such as courses, lectures and activities related to the transition program. The advantage is that it can help teachers, parents and others to add the information to be better prepared in the run transition program for students with special needs. Finally, the implementation of a career transition program for students with special needs to be seen in greater detail. It is the responsibility and the expectations of all parties to ensure that the special needs student outcomes in the future may contribute to the development of the next country to raise the name of special education in the world.

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